

STUDIES IN SULPHANILAMIDES. PART IX. N¹-SULPHANILAMIDE
DERIVATIVES OF PHENYL DIALKYLTHIOL PSEUDODITHIOBIURETS

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p-Acetsulphanilyl chloride has been condensed with seven N¹-phenyldialkylthiol *pseudodithio*-biurets to form phenyl N¹-acetsulphanilyl dialkylthiol *pseudodithio*biurets. The free bases from these have been obtained by hydrolysis with 10% aqueous or alcoholic hydrochloric acid.

The work described in this part was undertaken in pursuance of a programme of research to investigate the pharmacological properties of N¹-sulphanilamide derivatives

of open-chain compounds containing the group $\begin{array}{c} \text{N} \\ \diagup \\ \text{C} \\ \diagdown \\ \text{N} \end{array} - \text{S} \text{ (C or N)}$ which is present

in most of the active sulphanilamide drugs (*cf.* part VIII). Though quite a large number of N¹-heterocyclic derivatives of sulphanilamide containing this grouping are described in literature, only a few of the open-chain type seem to have been prepared, *e.g.* sulphanilamide derivatives of alkylthiol pseudothiureas, alkylthiol thiosemicarbazides and N-aryl-1-alkylthiol pseudothiureas (*Curr. Sci.*, 1943, 12, 325; 1944, 13, 205; *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 64, 1682; *Rev. Med. France*, 1941, Nov.-Dec.). Haworth and McGeorge (*Lancet*, 1943, 245, 465; 1942, 243, 30) have shown that thiourea and alkylthiol pseudothiureas are endowed with valuable therapeutic properties. Thiourea has also been shown to be an effective remedy against thyrotoxicosis and in combination with sulphathiazole it seems to act synergistically by inhibiting the growth of *B. coli* (Lee and Foley, *Proc. Soc. Exptl. Biol. Med.*, 1943, 54, 105). It was thought worthwhile therefore to prepare N¹-sulphanilamide derivatives of alkylthiol compounds of alkyl and aryl *pseudodithio*biurets.

For the purpose of preparing N¹-sulphanilamide derivatives, it is obvious that the unsubstituted and the monoalkylthiol derivatives of *pseudodithio*biurets (both

will not be of much use, since these are definitely acidic and will not condense with *p*-acetsulphanilyl chloride. It was expected, however, that substitution at both the sulphur atoms by alkyl groups in aryl*dithio*biurets would furnish compounds possessing pronounced basic character and hence should condense with *p*-acetsulphanilyl chloride. This expectation has now been realised.

There are two possible methods of preparing the dialkylthiol compounds in both of which the monoalkylthiol compounds are first prepared and then again alkylated. It is easily seen from the accepted formula of phenyldithio*biuret* that two structurally different (excluding tautomeric forms) monoalkylthiol *pseudodithio*biurets are possible, *viz.* (I) and (II),

according as the substitution is at S(i) or S(ii). Each on further alkylation gives the same dialkylthiol compound, as described in the experimental part. The preparation of compounds analogous to (II) depends on the reaction, studied by Johnson (*Amer. Chem. J.*, 1903, 30, 167) between unsubstituted pseudothiureas and isothiocyanates. For example, ethylthiol pseudothiurea combines with phenylisothiocyanate to give phenyl-2-ethylthiol pseudodithiobiuret (III),

This compound on further ethylation yields the diethylthiol compound. Compounds of type (I) are prepared by direct alkylation of mono-*o*-nitrogen aryl substituted dithiobiurets in the presence of ammonia or sodium hydroxide (*Ber.*, 1884, 17, 585). For example, phenyldithiobiuret gives phenyl-1-thioethyl pseudodithiobiuret (IV) on treatment with an equimolecular amount of ethyl iodide.

This on further ethylation gives a product, identical with that obtained by ethylating its isomer (III).

The structure of phenyldialkylthiol pseudodithiobiurets immediately follows from the structures of the two isomeric monoalkylthiol compounds which have been assigned structures (I) and (II) by Johnson. The action of alkyl halide on the two isomeric monoalkylthiol compounds can proceed in various ways to give structurally different products. But identical dialkyl derivatives will be produced in both cases if only the alkyl group gets attached to the other sulphur atom. That the same product is obtained by ethylation of the isomeric phenylmonoethylthiol pseudodithiobiurets convincingly shows that the dialkyl compounds are to be formulated as follows :

As anticipated, the phenyldialkylthiol pseudodithiobiurets proved to be strong bases and condensed with *p*-acetsulphanilyl chloride. Seven dialkyl derivatives have been prepared with methyl, ethyl, propyl, butyl, allyl, benzyl, and methylene as substituents. These are generally obtained by direct alkylation of phenyldithiobiuret with slightly more than two molecular proportion of alkyl halide in the presence of ammonia or sodium hydroxide solution without isolating the monoalkylthiol compound. The structurally isomeric monothiol compounds have been prepared, with ethyl as substituent, as mentioned in a preceding paragraph, to establish the identity with each other of the products obtained on further ethylation of each and also with that obtained by direct ethylation of phenyldithiobiuret with excess of ethyl bromide.

The condensation of each of these with *p*-acetsulphanilyl chloride is effected in acetone solution in the presence of pyridine. The reaction is initiated in a well cooled solution and allowed to continue for 12 hours at room temperature, after which the reaction mixture is poured into a large volume of water when the condensation product separates out. The latter is well washed with dilute alcohol and crystallised from alcohol or acetic acid.

The hydrolysis of the acetamino compounds has usually been accomplished by warming to 50-70° with 10% aqueous hydrochloric acid for about 15-30 minutes till a clear solution is obtained. The latter is then neutralised with 10% aqueous sodium hydroxide under cooling when the free base separates out and is crystallised from alcohol after filtration.

Invariably in each case the hydrolysis of the acetamino compounds takes place concurrently with their partial decomposition as is indicated by the strong smell of mercaptans and mustard oils. The conditions of hydrolysis have to be very carefully adjusted to produce the maximum yield of the free base.

All the free bases are insoluble in alkali. This indicates that there is no amido hydrogen present in the molecule and since tautomeric forms can be excluded for phenyl-dialkylthiol pseudodithiobiurets on the basis of Johnson's work on the hydrolysis of the isomeric monoalkylthiol derivatives (*loc. cit.*), the number of alternative structures for the sulphanilamide derivatives is reduced to two, *viz.*, (V) and (VI).

To decide between the two, a crucial experiment has been devised. The sulphanilamide derivative of phenyldiethylthiol pseudodithiobiuret is boiled with 10% alcoholic hydrochloric acid for half an hour. The solution, which smells of mercaptan, is neutralised with ammonia and the resulting precipitate crystallised from hot water. The substance thus isolated has the same melting point as sulphanilamide and does not depress the melting point of an authentic sample of the latter. The formation of sulphanilamide on hydrolysis indicates that structure (VI) is more probable for these sulphur compounds. The reaction can be visualised to take place initially as follows :

followed by the decomposition of the dialkyl derivative into mercaptans, isothiocyanates, etc.

EXPERIMENTAL

Phenyldithiobiuret was prepared adopting the procedure described in *Annalen*, 1893, 275, 43.

N^a-Phenyl-1 : 2-diethylthiol pseudodithiobiuret was prepared by ethylation of the two isomeric monoethylthiol compounds and also by direct ethylation of phenyldithiobiuret. Phenyl monoethylthiol pseudodithiobiuret (either of the isomers prepared as described in *Ber.*, 1884, 17, 585 ; *Amer. Chem. J.*, 1903, 30, 167), was dissolved in a mixture of alcohol and ammonia and boiled with slightly more than 1 molecule of ethyl bromide for 3-4 hours. The mixture was cooled and poured into water when crystals mixed with oil settled down. On standing for some time in an ice-bath, complete solidification took

place. The solid was separated, treated with 10% sodium hydroxide solution and the solution filtered. The undissolved residue was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 165°, yield 40-45%.

The same substance was obtained by treating phenyldithiobiuret with slightly more than 2 moles of ethyl bromide. Phenyldithiobiuret (5 g.) dissolved in alcohol (40 c.c.) was treated with liquor ammonia (8 c.c.) and ethyl bromide (7 g.). After about 70 minutes, the reaction mixture was diluted with water (200 c.c.) and left in ice for sometime. The solid was freed from the mono compound by treatment with 10% sodium hydroxide in which it dissolved, and the residue crystallised from alcohol twice, m.p. 165-66°, yield 1.5-2 g. (25-35%).

The identity with one another of the products obtained by the different methods was established by taking mixed melting points. In no case was any depression observed. (Found: C, 54.12; H, 6.53; N, 15.95; S, 24.09. $C_{12}H_{17}N_3S_2$ requires C, 53.94; H, 6.37; N, 15.73; S, 23.97 per cent).

N^a -Phenyl- N^c -(N^1 -*p*-acetsulphanilyl)-1 : 2-diethylthiol pseudodithiobiuret was obtained by interacting N^a -phenyl-1 : 2-diethylthiol pseudodithiobiuret (2.5 g.) in a mixture of acetone (25 c.c.) and pyridine (5c.c.) with *p*-acetsulphanilyl chloride (2.5 g.). The reaction was started under cooling (15-20°) and allowed to proceed afterwards at room temperature for 8 hours. On dilution with water, the red solution deposited a sticky resin-like product which was separated by decantation, washed with a small amount of alcohol and crystallised from the same solvent, m.p. 205°, yield 1.8 to 2.3 g. (Found: C, 51.91; H, 5.43; N, 12.3; S, 20.82. $C_{20}H_{24}O_3N_4S_3$ requires C, 51.72; H, 5.17; N, 12.1; S, 20.7 per cent).

N^a -Phenyl- N^c -(N^1 -sulphanilyl)-1 : 2-diethylthiol pseudodithiobiuret.—The above acetyl compound (2 g.) was hydrolysed by warming on a water-bath maintained at 60-70° with 10% aqueous hydrochloric acid (15 c.c.) for half an hour, the clear solution was neutralised with 10% sodium hydroxide under cooling when the free base was precipitated. A single crystallisation from alcohol gave the pure substance, m.p. 153°, yield 1.1 g. (Found: C, 50.96; H, 5.1; N, 13.3; S, 22.98. $C_{18}H_{22}O_2N_4S_3$ requires C, 51.2; H, 5.21; N, 13.3; S, 22.8 per cent).

It was thought worthwhile oxidising N^c -phenyl-1-ethylthiol pseudodithiobiuret, which contains a sulphhydryl group, to the disulphide and trying to condense this with *p*-acetsulphanilyl chloride. The condensation was sought to be effected under the same conditions as obtained in the above condensation but no condensation product could be isolated.

bis-(N^a -Phenyl-1-ethylthiol pseudodithiobiuret)-2-disulphide Hydriodide.—To a hot saturated solution of the monoethylthiol compound in alcohol, was added an alcoholic solution of iodine till there was no more decolorisation. The solution was allowed to cool when crystals separated. These were filtered and recrystallised from alcohol, m.p. 129-30°, yield quantitative. (Found: N, 11.56. $C_{20}H_{22}N_6I_2S_4$ requires N, 11.48 per cent).

N^a -Phenyl-1 : 2-dimethylthiol pseudodithiobiuret.—Phenyldithiobiuret (10 g.) was dissolved in a mixture of 40% aqueous sodium hydroxide solution (15 c.c.) and alcohol (90 c.c.) and warmed with dimethyl sulphate (7 g.) on a water-bath for 3 hours. The solution was treated with acid till it was only slightly alkaline when a precipitate was

deposited. This was crystallised from alcohol after treatment with norit, m.p. 195° yield 7 g. (Found : N, 17.5. $C_{10}H_{13}N_3S_2$ requires N, 17.6 per cent).

N^a-Phenyl-*N*^c-(*N*¹-acetylulphanilyl)-1 : 2-dimethylthiol pseudodithiobiuret obtained from *N*^a-phenyl-1 : 2-dimethylthiol pseudodithiobiuret (2.5 g.) and *p*-acetylulphanilyl chloride (2.5 g.) in acetone solution (30 c.c.) in presence of pyridine (5 c.c.), m.p. 186°, yield 2.5 g. (Found : N, 12.62. $C_{16}H_{20}O_3N_4S_3$ requires N, 12.8 per cent).

N^a-Phenyl-*N*^c-(sulphanilyl)-1 : 2-dimethylthiol pseudodithiobiuret.—The above acet amino compound (2 g.) was hydrolysed by refluxing with 10% alcoholic hydrochloric acid (13 c.c.) on a water-bath till the solution cleared. The solution was neutralised with 10% aqueous sodium hydroxide and the resulting precipitate crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 124°, yield 0.9 g. (Found : N, 14.13. $C_{16}H_{18}O_3N_3S_3$ requires N, 14.21 per cent).

N^a-Phenyl-1 : 2-dipropylthiol pseudodithiobiuret was obtained by refluxing solution of phenyldithiobiuret (6 g.) in a mixture of 40% sodium hydroxide (10 c.c.) and alcohol (60 c.c.) with *n*-propyl iodide (12 g.) for 1 hour and diluting with water. The substance separated as an oil and did not completely solidify even on standing in ice. It was separated by decantation, treated with a further amount of alkali (10%) to remove traces of monopropylthiol compound, washed with water and dried in a desiccator over potassium hydroxide for 2 days. The semisolid which was thus obtained was directly condensed with *p*-acetylulphanilyl chloride, yield 3.5 g.

N^a-Phenyl-1-*n*-propylthiol pseudodithiobiuret.—The alkaline washings in the last experiment deposited on neutralisation with acid the 1-propylthiol compound which was purified by crystallisation from alcohol, m.p. 81°. (Found : N, 16.53. $C_{11}H_{15}N_3S_2$ requires N, 16.6 per cent).

bis-(*N*^a-phenyl-1-*n*-propylthiol pseudodithiobiuret)-2-disulphide hydriodide was prepared by oxidising an alcoholic solution of the 1-propylthiol compound with iodine, m.p. 101°, yield quantitative. (Found : N, 11.18. $C_{22}H_{30}N_6I_2S_4$ requires N, 11.05 per cent).

N^a-Phenyl-*N*^c-(*N*¹-acetylulphanilyl)-1 : 2-*n*-dipropylthiol pseudodithiobiuret was obtained by condensing *p*-acetylulphanilyl chloride (2.6 g.) with the crude *N*^a-phenyl-1 : 2-*n*-dipropylthiol pseudodithiobiuret (3 g.) in acetone solution (30 c.c.) in presence of pyridine (5 c.c.). The acetyl derivative was isolated and purified as usual as white crystals, m.p. 178°, yield 2.4 g. (Found : N, 11.45. $C_{22}H_{26}O_3N_4S_3$ requires N, 11.39 per cent).

N^a-Phenyl-*N*^c-(*N*¹-sulphanilyl)-1 : 2-*n*-dipropylthiol pseudodithiobiuret.—The above acetyl compound (2 g.) was hydrolysed with 10% alcoholic hydrochloric acid (15 c.c.) by boiling gently on a water-bath for 20-30 minutes, m. p. 137-38°, yield 0.6 g. (Found : N, 12.62. $C_{20}H_{26}O_3N_4S_3$ requires N, 12.5 per cent).

N^a-Phenyl-1 : 2-*n*-dibutylthiol dipseudodithiobiuret.—Phenyldithiobiuret (5 g.) was refluxed in a 6% alcoholic sodium hydroxide solution (70 c.c.) with normal butyl iodide (12 g.) for ½ hour and left to stand overnight at room temperature. The solution was diluted with water and acidified till it was only slightly alkaline when a precipitate was deposited. This was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 85°, yield 4.5 g. (Found : N, 13.06. $C_{16}H_{22}N_3S_2$ requires N, 13.0 per cent).

N^a-Phenyl-*N*^c-(*N*¹-acetylulphanilyl)-1 : 2-*n*-dibutylthiol pseudodithiobiuret was obtained in the usual manner from the above mentioned dibutylthiol compound (5.25 g.)

and *p*-acetsulphanilyl chloride (4 g.), m.p. 216°, yield 4.7 g. (Found : N, 10.61. $C_{24}H_{22}O_3N_4S_3$ requires N, 10.76 per cent).

N^a-Phenyl-*N*^c-(*N*¹-sulphanilyl)-1 : 2-*n*-dibutylthiol pseudodithiobiuret.—The acetyl compound (4.2 g.) was hydrolysed with 10% aqueous hydrochloric acid (25 c.c.), m.p. 148°, yield 1.5 g. (Found : N, 11.74. $C_{22}H_{30}O_2N_4S_3$ requires N, 11.71 per cent).

N^a-Phenyl-1 : 2-*diallylthiol pseudodithiobiuret* was prepared by gently refluxing a solution of phenyldithiobiuret (5 g.) in 6% alcoholic sodium hydroxide solution (70 c.c.) with allyl chloride (5 g.) for 2 hours, m.p. 110°, yield 3 g. (Found : N, 14.51. $C_{14}H_{17}N_3S_2$ requires N, 14.43 per cent).

N^a-Phenyl-*N*^c-(*N*¹-acetsulphanilyl) 1 : 2-*diallylthiol pseudodithiobiuret* was obtained by condensing acetsulphanilyl chloride (2.5 g.) in a solution of *N*^a-phenyl-1 : 2-*diallylthiol pseudodithiobiuret* (3 g.) in a mixture of acetone (30 c.c.) and pyridine (5 c.c.). Initial refluxing for an hour was necessary, m.p. 192°, yield 2.1 g. (Found : N, 11.53. $C_{22}H_{24}O_2N_4S_3$ requires N, 11.48 per cent).

N^a-Phenyl-*N*^c-(*N*¹-sulphanilyl)-1 : 2-*diallylthiol pseudodithiobiuret*.—The corresponding acetamino compound (2 g.) was kept overnight suspended in 10% alcoholic hydrochloric acid (25 c.c.). The solution was later filtered and the free base obtained from the filtrate and purified as usual. The substance was initially obtained in the form of an oil which on standing in an ice-bath solidified, m.p. 122°, yield 0.7 g. (Found : N, 12.72. $C_{20}H_{22}O_2N_4S_3$ requires N, 12.56 per cent).

N^a-Phenyl-1 : 2-*dibenzylthiol pseudodithiobiuret* was obtained from benzyl chloride (6 g.) and phenyldithiobiuret (5 g.) as usual, m.p. 180°, yield 3.5 g. (Found : N, 10.81. $C_{22}H_{21}N_3S_2$ requires N, 10.74 per cent).

N^a-Phenyl-*N*^c-(*N*¹-acetsulphanilyl)-1 : 2-*dibenzylthiol pseudodithiobiuret* was obtained by the action of *p*-acetsulphanilyl chloride (1.8 g.) on *N*^a-phenyl-1 : 2-*dibenzylthiol pseudodithiobiuret* (3 g.) dissolved in a mixture of acetone (20 c.c.) and pyridine (4c.c.), m.p. 224°, yield 1.8 g. (Found : N, 9.6. $C_{30}H_{28}O_3N_4S_3$ requires N, 9.52 per cent).

N^a-Phenyl-*N*^c-(*N*¹-sulphanilyl)-1 : 2-*dibenzylthiol pseudodithiobiuret* was obtained by the hydrolysis of the acetamino compound (1.8 g.) with 10% aqueous HCl (15 c.c.), m.p. 129°, yield 0.8 g. (Found : N, 10.07. $C_{28}H_{26}O_2N_4S_3$ requires N, 10.26 per cent).

N^a-Phenyl-1 : 2-*dimethylenethiol pseudodithiobiuret*.—Methylene iodide (10 g.) was boiled with a solution of phenyldithiobiuret (5 g.) in 6% alcoholic sodium hydroxide (70 c.c.) for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour and the solution left to stand by itself for 8 hours ; it was later diluted with water when a precipitate settled down and was separated and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 89°, yield 4 g. (Found : N, 18.85. $C_9H_9N_3S_2$ requires N, 18.83 per cent).

N^a-Phenyl-*N*^c-(*N*¹-acetsulphanilyl)-1 : 2-*dimethylenethiol pseudodithiobiuret* was obtained by treating a solution of *N*^a-phenyl-1 : 2-*dimethylenethiol pseudodithiobiuret* (2.2 g.) in a mixture of acetone (25 c.c.) and pyridine (5 c.c.) with *p*-acetsulphanilyl chloride (2.2 g.). Initial refluxing for half an hour was found advantageous. The acetamino compound was isolated and purified as usual, m.p. 238°, yield 2.3 g. (Found : N, 13.52. $C_{17}H_{16}O_3N_4S_3$ requires N, 13.34 per cent).

N^a-Phenyl-*N*^c-(*N*¹-sulphanilyl)-1 : 2-*dimethylenethiol pseudodithiobiuret*.—The above acetyl compound (2 g.) was hydrolysed by refluxing with 10% alcoholic hydrochloric

acid (20 c.c.) for 20-30 minutes. The base was precipitated on neutralisation with alkali and was purified by crystallisation from alcohol after treatment with norit, m. p. 179-180°, yield 0.75 g (Found : N, 14.72. $C_{13}H_{14}O_2N_4S_2$ requires N, 14.81 per cent).

Hydrolysis of N'-Phenyl-N-(N'-sulphanilyl)-1:2-diethylthiol pseudodithiobiuret—The sulpho compound (1 g.) was refluxed with alcoholic hydrochloric acid (30 c.c.) for 20 minutes. The solution turned red and a strong smell of mercaptan was felt. The solution was then filtered and the filtrate made alkaline with ammonia when a precipitate resulted. Concentration of the solution yielded more of the substance which was crystallised from hot water after treatment with norit, m. p. 159-60°. A mixed melting point was taken with an authentic sample of sulphanilamide and no depression was observed.

N'-p-Tolyl-1:2-diethylthiol pseudodithiobiuret.—It may not be out of place here to record an observation in connection with *N'-p-tolyl-1-ethylthiol pseudodithiobiuret* which Tursini (*Ber.*, 1884, 17, 585) was the first to prepare. His method of preparation yielded a substance which he states melted at 134° and which was verified by the authors. This substance was, however, suspected to be a mixture of the mono and the dithiol compounds and was sought to be purified by dissolving in 10% alkali and examining the alkali-soluble and insoluble portions separately. The alkaline solution on acidifying deposited the monoethyl compound which after crystallisation from alcohol melted at 138°. The alkali-insoluble portion after crystallisation from alcohol was analysed, m.p. 185°. (Found : N, 15.07. $C_{13}H_{14}N_4S_2$ requires N, 14.95 per cent).